

CONDUCTING GESTURES AND THEIR FUNCTIONS**Hamdamov Doniyor Shahobjon ugli**

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ABSTRACT

This article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of conducting gestures as the main component of conducting art and their functions in the process of musical performance. The study examines the types of conducting gestures, their role in revealing the content of a musical composition, and their significance in managing and coordinating performers' activities. In addition, the pedagogical potential of conducting technique in shaping rhythm, dynamics, tempo, phrasing, and expressiveness is revealed. The article scientifically substantiates the aesthetic and communicative features of conducting gestures and their impact on the quality of ensemble performance.

Introduction.

The art of music is one of the most subtle and complex manifestations of human culture, which in the process of performance embodies not only the harmony of sounds, but also creative thinking, aesthetic taste and collective cooperation. In this complex process, the conductor's personality occupies a central place, he appears as the main controlling force directing the artistic thinking of the group of performers towards a common goal. The conductor's main means of communication is not words, but actions - that is, the actions of the conductor.

Conducting actions are a unique expressive language that enlivens the musical text, conveys its inner content and emotional layers to the performers [1]. Each movement, gesture and gesture serve to reveal the rhythmic structure, tempo, dynamic development and artistic image of the musical work. Therefore, conducting actions should be evaluated not only as a technical skill, but also as a complex communicative process with a deep artistic, aesthetic and psychological content.

Today, the demands on the art of conducting in the music education system are increasing. The expansion of collective performance forms, the development of choral and orchestral culture require the conductor not only musical literacy, but also a high level of movement culture, pedagogical skills and leadership competencies. Especially in the process of training future music teachers, a thorough mastery of the content and tasks of conducting movements is emerging as an important

methodological issue. From this point of view, a scientific analysis of the essence of conducting movements, their functional tasks in the process of musical performance and their significance in the educational process is one of the urgent issues. After all, through conducting movements, the musical idea is not only controlled, but also educated, interpreted and formed as a single artistic vision in the minds of performers.

Literature and source analysis.

The art of conducting and the issue of conducting movements have been studied by many researchers in the fields of music performance, pedagogy, and art history, and a rich scientific, theoretical, and methodological heritage has been formed in this area. An analysis of the existing literature shows that conducting movements have been interpreted based on various approaches as a means of controlling musical performance.

Conductors and researchers such as H. Shyerkhen [1; 198], I. Musin, N. Malko, K. Kondrashin [6], representatives of the European music school, considered conducting movements in their works as the main means of expression of musical thought and performance. In particular, I. Musin's scientific works on conducting technique are focused on the formation of the accuracy, logic and expressiveness of conducting movements, and he interprets conducting gestures as the external manifestation of musical thought [4; 97]. N. Malko, on the other hand, pays special attention to the role of conducting movements in rhythmic accuracy and tempo control, substantiating the inextricable link between movement and sound [5].

Research conducted within the framework of the Russian music-pedagogical school has widely covered the methodological and didactic aspects of conducting movements. Such scientists and practicing conductors as K. Kondrashin [6] and G. Rozhdestvensky put forward in their works the issue of the inner artistic thinking of the conductor and its manifestation through actions [7]. In this approach, conducting actions are considered not only as a technical tool, but also as an important mechanism for establishing psychological contact with performers.

Special attention is also paid to this issue in studies conducted on Uzbek music pedagogy and the art of conducting. Local researchers have covered the methodology of working with choirs and orchestras, the role of conducting actions in the educational process, and the formation of conducting skills in future music teachers. In particular, the flexibility and expressiveness of conducting actions are indicated as an important factor in interpreting national musical thinking, maqoms, and folk music samples in collective performance.

In modern scientific sources, the issue of conducting actions is interpreted based on communicative and interactive approaches. In the management of the musical performance process, such aspects as nonverbal communication, the semantics of

gestures, and the psychological impact of the conductor's actions are at the center of new scientific research. This creates the need to study the conductor's actions not only as a musical-technical, but also as a pedagogical and socio-cultural phenomenon.

Discussion.

Although the conductor's actions seem to be the external appearance of the musical performance, in fact, their content is a complex process closely related to the internal artistic thinking, musical imagination, and emotional state. The conductor, through each of his actions on stage, not only controls musical time and space, but also forms a single artistic image in the minds of the performers. From this point of view, the conductor's actions appear as the central communicative mechanism of the performance process.

During the discussion, it was found that the effectiveness of conducting movements depends more on their harmony with the musical content than on their mechanical accuracy. Movements that determine rhythm and tempo should not only be a means of maintaining the metric order, but also reveal the inner breath of the musical work. If the conductor's movements correspond to the logical development of the musical phrase, the musical text will be interpreted more freely and naturally by the performers. On the contrary, the discrepancy between movement and sound leads to a violation of artistic integrity in collective performance.

Another important aspect of conducting movements is their expressive and psychological impact. The plasticity, amplitude and energy level of the conductor's movements directly affect the internal state of the performers. For example, wide and free movements enhance the solemn or lyrical character of the music, while concise and precise gestures provide dramatic or rhythmic tension. This allows us to consider conducting movements as a means of aesthetic education [3].

From a pedagogical point of view, the process of teaching conducting movements should not be limited to the formation of technical skills. A future music teacher or conductor should understand the musical meaning of each movement and learn to perform it consciously. The results of the discussion show that teaching conducting movements based on an analytical and reflexive approach has a positive effect on the development of students' musical thinking. In modern music education, the communicative function of conducting movements is becoming increasingly important. In the process of working with a team, the conductor creates a discipline, trust, and creative environment through unspoken communication. This makes it possible to evaluate conducting movements as a tool for developing leadership and management competencies.

Conclusion.

The results of the study show that conducting movements are an important and integral part of the musical performance process, through which the artistic content, rhythmic structure, tempo-dynamic development, and emotional state of a musical work are conveyed to the performers. Conducting movements are not only a means of technical control, but also an effective communicative mechanism of musical thinking and aesthetic expression. In conclusion, conducting movements are considered a multifunctional, complex and systematic phenomenon in the process of musical performance and education. Their study on a scientific, theoretical and methodological basis is of great importance, especially in the conditions of modern music education, in improving the professional training of future specialists. The results of this study serve as a theoretical and practical basis for a deeper understanding of the art of conducting and its effective implementation in educational practice..

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